

POSITION CONTROL OF PARABOLIC DISH ANTENNA USING FEEDBACK, ZEIGLER-NICHOLS AND QUADRATIC OPTIMAL REGULATOR METHODS

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ABSTRACT

A unity feedback servomotor actuated parabolic dish antenna system was modeled, and two different types of controllers were designed for the system using; Ziegler-Nichols and Quadratic Optimal Regulator methods for the close loop operation of the system. Their responses were simulated using the software package MATLAB 7.1. Simulation results showed that each of the controllers greatly improved the system response. Best system responses were obtained via the Quadratic Optimal Regulator method.

KEYWORDS: Controller, Quadratic Optimal Regulator, Servomotor, Ziegler-Nichols Method.

INTRODUCTION

The advancement in satellite technology has made the whole world become a global village such that events happening at a particular location can be monitored as it happens in other locations. These satellites are normally stationed far above the earth in geosynchronous orbit. Therefore signals reaching the earth are very weak; hence reception of these signals requires the use of antennas with very high gains. The parabolic dish antennas give high gains at microwave frequencies with comparatively small dimensions, and at microwave frequencies receives maximum signal field when positioned in the line-of-sight of the transmission satellite. Servomotors are used to position these dish antennas and therefore steady state positional errors should be minimized. The use of parabolic antennas is not limited to satellite communications. It also finds applications in radar systems, long distance communication (e.g. telephony) and so on (Hart, 2000). The use of these systems have the advantages of minimizing human error and energy, quick and easier repositioning to another direction or its initial position in case the antenna is displaced by disturbances such as wind, gust, bearing and aerodynamic frictions and so on (Gawronski, 2004).

Figure 1: Illustration of Servomotor Actuated Parabolic Antenna

A controller (compensator) is a device or sub-system inserted into a system in order to modify the system dynamics. There are many methods used in control systems analysis and design such as; the root-locus method, frequency-response method, the state space method and PID compensation methods (Mandal, 2006).

2. Dynamic Model of the System

The equivalent circuit of field controlled D.C. servomotor is as shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 2: Equivalent Circuit of Field Controlled D.C. Servomotor Actuated Antenna

Consider the figure 2 above;

$$V_f = K_1 D_i \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

$$R_f I_f + S L_f I_f \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Equating (1) and (2) and I_f the subject

$$I_f = \frac{(K_1 D_i)}{(R_f + S L_f)} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where;

I_f is the motor field current,

L_f is the motor field inductance,

R_f is the motor field resistance,

D_i is the control input.

The electromechanical torque developed by the motor is proportional to the motor current (Gopal and Nagrath, 2003). Therefore;

$$T_m = K_m I_f \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where;

T_m is the electromechanical torque and K_m the motor torque constant.

The electromechanical dynamics of the antenna system is given as;

$$T_m = J \frac{d^2 \theta_0}{dt^2} + F \frac{d\theta_0}{dt} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Taking the laplace transform,

$$T_m = JS^2 \theta_0 + FS \theta_0 \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Equating (4) and (6), we have;

$$JS^2 \theta_0 + FS \theta_0 = K_m I_f \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

Substituting (3) in (7);

Therefore;

$$JS^2 \theta_0 + FS \theta_0 = \frac{(K_1 K_m D_i)}{(R_f + S L_f)} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

Hence;

$$\frac{\theta_0}{D_i} = \frac{(K_1 K_m)}{(R_f + S L_f) S (S J + F)} \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

Where;

J is the moment of inertia of the antenna system (load) referred to the shaft of the servomotor,
 F is the coefficient of damping of the antenna system (load) referred to the shaft of the servomotor,
 N is the motor-to-load gear ratio.

Equation (9) can be expressed as;

$$\theta_0 = G_1 G_2 D_i \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

$$G_1 = \frac{(K_1)}{(R_f + SL_f)} \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

$$G_2 = \frac{(K_m)}{(S(SJ + F))} \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

For a unity feedback the block diagram is as shown below;

Figure 3: Block Diagram of the Unity Feedback Closed Loop System

The Plant transfer function $G_1 G_2$ is given as;

$$G_1 G_2 = \frac{(K_1 K_m)}{(S^3 JL_f + S^2(L_f F + JR_f) + SFR_f)} = \frac{136.8}{S^3 + 15S^2 + 50S} \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

The closed loop transfer function becomes;

$$\frac{\theta_o}{D_i} = \frac{K_1 K_m / JL_f}{S^3 + S^2 \left(\frac{F}{J} + \frac{R_f}{L_f} \right) + S \left(\frac{R_f F}{JL_f} \right) + \left(\frac{K_1 K_m}{JL_f} \right)} \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

Using the parameters in tables 1 and 2, the transfer function becomes;

$$\frac{\theta_o}{D_i} = \frac{136.8}{(S^3 + 15S^2 + 50S + 136.8)} \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

The characteristics of servomotor and the parameters of a typical parabolic dish antenna are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 Characteristics of Servomotor

PARAMETER	VALUE
Motor field resistance R_f	100Ω
Motor field inductance L_f	20H
Motor torque constant K_m	20Nm/A
Motor-to-load gear ratio N	1:50

Table 2 Parameters of Typical Parabolic Dish Antenna

PARAMETER	VALUE
Dish Moment of inertia J_D	250kgm ²
Dish Damping Coefficient F_D	2500Nms ⁻¹ rad ⁻¹
Depth of dish L_D	1.4m
Dish Diameter D	1.1m

Source: (Agee, *et al.*, 1992)

Ziegler-Nichols Method

A PID control is a proportional integral plus derivative controller whose transfer function is:

$$G_{pid}(S) = K_p \left(1 + T_d S + \frac{1}{T_i S} \right) \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

Ziegler-Nichols method is one of the techniques used for tuning these PID controllers. Consider the figure below:

Figure 4: Unity feedback Closed Loop System

The values of the PID controller proportional constant K_p , integral time T_i and derivative time T_d can be determined using Ziegler-Nichols technique (Burns 2001).

The method can be sub-classified into two:

First method: this method is used if the step response of the plant results into an S-shaped curve as shown below:

Figure 5: Illustration of The S-shaped Response Curve

It is characterized by two constants; the delay time M and the time constant N . Therefore the controller parameters can be obtained using;

$$K_p = \frac{(1.2N)}{M}, T_i = 2M \text{ And } T_d = 0.5M \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

Second method: if the condition in the first method is not satisfied then this method can be used. Using this technique the critical period T_c corresponding to the critical value of the proportional constant K_c is first determined, and is obtained by setting $T_i = \text{infinity}$, $T_d = \text{zero}$ and varying K_p from zero to critical value K_c . At

the critical point the output of the plant becomes oscillatory in nature. The controller parameters are then obtained using; $K_p = 0.6K_c$, $T_i = 0.5T_c$ and $T_d = 0.125T_c$ (18)

QUADRATIC OPTIMAL REGULATOR SYSTEM

Consider a control system represented in state space as;

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= Ax + Bu \\ y &= Cx + Du \end{aligned} \dots\dots\dots(19)$$

Where; x = state vector (m-vector), y = output signal (scalar), u = control signal (scalar),
 A = m by m constant matrix, B = m by 1 constant matrix, C = 1 by m matrix,
 D = constant (scalar)

If the control signal is chosen to be;

$$u(t) = -Kx(t) \dots\dots\dots (20)$$

It means that the control signal u is determined by an instantaneous state, and such a scheme is called state feedback. The 1 by m matrix K is called the space feedback gain matrix. Assuming that all the state variables are available for feedback and also u is not constrained. The block of the optimal configuration system is as shown in figure 6.

Figure 6: Quadratic Optimal Regulator Systems

Controlling the system using the optimal regulator technique, the system equation (19) determines the matrix K of the optimal control vector (20), so as to minimize the performance index,

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} (x^* Q x + u^* R u) dt \dots\dots\dots (21)$$

Where; Q is a positive-definite (or positive-semi-definite) Hermitian or real symmetric matrix and R is a positive-definite Hermitian or real symmetric matrix. The term $(u^* R u)$ accounts for the expenditure of the energy of the control signals. The matrices Q and R determine the relative importance of the error and the expenditure of this energy.

The linear control law given equation (20) is the optimal control law. Therefore, if the unknown elements of the matrix K are determine so as to determine the performance index, then $u(t) = -Kx(t)$ is optimal for any initial state $x(0)$. Solving equations (19), (20), and (21) using matrix Ricatti method, we have;

$$u(t) = -Kx(t) = -R^{-1} B^* P x(t) \dots\dots\dots (22)$$

$$A^* P + PA - PBR^{-1} B^* P + Q = 0 \dots\dots\dots (23)$$

The system is stable if matrix P is positive definite or matrix $A - BK$ is stable. Equation (23) is called the reduced-matrix Ricatti equation (Katsuhiko, 2010).

SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A simulation of the unity feedback system response was performed using MATLAB 7.1 with the controller designed using the Ziegler-Nichols (ZN controller) and the Quadratic Optimal Regulator (QO controller) methods. The closed loop unity feedback unit step response of the system is shown in Figure 7, with the ZN controller in Figure 8 and with QO controller in Figure 9. So it can be concluded that Ziegler-Nichols and the Quadratic Optimal Regulator methods are suitable to design a self-tuning technique for the system, where the speed of response has tremendously increased, and the steady state error approaches zero.

Figure 7: Unity Feedback Response.

Figure 8: Response with ZN Controller.

Figure 9: Response with QO Controller.

The result can be summarized and tabulated as shown in Table 3.

Parameter	Unity Feedback	With ZN Controller	With QO Controller
Rise Time (s)	0.7900	0.2550	0.6150
Peak Time (s)	1.1450	0.4100	0.8050
Maximum Over Shoot (%)	14.77	18.88	4.27
Settling Time (s)	2.4900	1.9300	1.0650

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a mathematical model of the servomotor actuated parabolic dish antenna system was developed. The simulation of the system was done using the software package Matlab 7.1. ZN and Quadratic Optimal

Controllers were presented and applied to the system. The controllers designed have been simulated and observed to have good performance, where the results show that the rise time, peak time, maximum overshoot and settling times are; 0.7900 second, 1.1450 seconds, 14.77% and 2.4900 seconds respectively for the unity feedback system. With the ZN controller the results are; 0.2550 seconds, 0.4100 seconds, 18.88% and 1.9300 seconds that using the QO controller are 0.6150 seconds, 0.8050 seconds, 4.27% and 1.0650 seconds, which shows that the response had improved drastically with the controllers. And the results have shown that the QO controller gives the best response. Hence, a position controller has been designed successfully for closed loop operation of the system and it runs faster and very close to the reference position.

REFERENCES

- Agee, T. (1992). Stabilization of Dish Antennas in Windy Environment. Masters Degree Thesis, Unpublished.
- Burns, R. S. (2001). Advanced Control Engineering. (First Edition). Butterworth-Heinemann Publishers, Oxford. Pages 88-93.
- Gawronski, W. (2004). Control and Pointing Challenges of Antennas and (Radio) Telescopes, IPN Progress Report 42-159.
- Gopal, M. and Nagrath, I. J. (2003) Control System Engineering. (Third Edition). New Age International Limited Publishers, New Delhi.
- Hart, D. (2000). Satellite Communications,
http://www.cis.ohio-state.edu/~jain/cis_788-97/satellite-nets/index.htm
- Katsuhiko, O. (2010). Modern Control Engineering. (Fifth edition). Prentice Hall Publishers New Jersey.
- Mandal, A. K. (2006). Introduction to Control Engineering, Modeling, Analysis and Design. New Age International Limited Publishers, New Delhi.
- Omizegba, E. E. (2010). Matlab Core. Paper presented at Matlab workshop organized by University Computer Centre (UCC), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.
- Stephen, J. C. (2009). Matlab Programming for Engineers. Bookware Companion Series, Second Edition.

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